

mediately after spraying and kept covered until maturity.

Percentages of discolored grains are given in Table 1. All three species of fungi caused discoloration when inoculated at flower, milk, and soft dough stages. *H. oryzae* caused maximum discoloration. Inoculation at flower stage caused more

discoloration than at milk stage or soft dough stage. Inoculation at dough stage produced no discoloration.

The influence of weather factors on grain discoloration in commonly grown rice varieties maturing at different months was studied throughout the year (Table 2). Panicles of the crops harvested from

October to December had more discolored grains. Low temperature, high humidity, high rainfall, and more rainy days prevailed during these months and appear to cause a higher percent of discoloration. Temperature range at flowering stage seemed to have more influence on the high incidence of grain discoloration.

Table 2. Grain discoloration in relation to weather factors.

Month	Temperature (°C)		Relative humidity (%)	Rainfall		Discolored grains (%)									
	Max	Min		mm	Rainy days (no.)	CO 39	Ponni	Bhavarii	IR8	IR20	Vaigai	TN1	Kannagi	Benni Bhog ^a	CO 13 ^b
Jun 1980	31.2	23.0	78	30.3	6	5	4	9	1	4	2	3	8	14	6
Jul	30.9	22.5	81	25.7	3	5	5	9	2	5	3	3	8	14	6
Aug	31.1	22.1	79	15.7	2	6	6	9	2	5	3	3	8	14	6
Sep	32.0	21.4	87	67.9	3	29	31	39	6	22	29	32	38	29	32
Oct	30.9	21.3	90	217.9	8	55	42	56	16	35	62	60	72	72	55
Nov	29.4	20.3	90	176.7	8	52	41	54	15	33	61	60	71	71	51
Dec	29.6	19.0	88	6.8	1	73	82	80	72	76	72	88	80	83	61
Jan 1981	30.1	18.1	87	0.2	1	32	33	29	12	30	33	33	30	43	31
Feb	32.6	17.0	77	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	2	0
Mar	34.3	20.8	83	21.4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

^a Susceptible check for *H. oryzae*. ^b Local check for blast.

Accumulation of phenolics in rice varieties due to infection by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*

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Phenolic compounds play a vital role in the defense mechanism of plants against infectious agents. The participation of phenolic compounds in bacterial leaf blight disease resistance was studied.

Rice varieties ASDS (moderately susceptible), CO 40 (susceptible), TN1

(highly susceptible), and TNAU7 124 (moderately resistant) were sown in pots and fertilized with 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha. Seedlings were clip inoculated with freshly isolated bacterial suspension 10⁸ cells/ml 15 days after seeding. Samples of leaves from the inoculated plants

Table 1. Effect of *X. oryzae* infection on total phenolics and ortho-dihydroxy phenols in rice varieties ^a

Variety	Plant stage ^b	Total content (µg/g leaf tissue) of											
		Phenol						Ortho-dihydroxy phenol					
		7 DI		10 DI		15 DI		7 DI		10 DI		15 DI	
		H	D	H	D	H	D	H	D	H	D	H	D
TNAU7124	S	2.67	3.30	2.51	2.84	2.51	2.62	1.65	1.87	1.91	2.25	2.42	2.31
	T	2.33	2.56	2.04	2.26	1.84	2.04	0.96	1.62	1.06	1.84	1.66	1.93
	B	2.51	2.92	2.25	2.53	2.12	2.34	0.74	1.46	0.72	0.73	0.46	0.60
ASD5	S	2.52	2.80	2.26	2.19	2.19	2.37	1.91	2.21	2.09	1.75	2.09	2.08
	T	2.51	2.54	2.23	2.31	2.18	2.15	1.18	1.98	1.52	1.98	1.36	1.59
	B	2.64	2.66	2.47	2.45	2.34	1.84	1.87	1.45	0.72	1.04	0.56	1.43
TN1	S	2.53	2.61	2.52	2.95	2.03	2.28	1.65	1.32	1.54	1.78	2.45	2.09
	T	2.33	1.97	2.30	1.90	2.11	2.29	1.55	1.73	1.26	1.36	1.15	1.56
	B	2.46	2.52	2.68	2.89	2.34	2.21	1.54	1.50	0.60	0.73	0.61	0.98
CO 40	S	2.64	2.85	2.83	2.64	2.49	2.24	1.43	1.80	2.14	2.21	2.14	2.21
	T	2.43	2.63	2.26	2.36	1.93	1.99	1.34	1.60	1.47	1.50	0.97	1.52
	B	2.29	2.32	2.34	2.46	2.10	2.24	1.50	1.54	2.04	2.06	0.98	0.61

^a DI = days after inoculation, H = healthy, D = diseased. ^b S = seedling, T = tillering, B = boot leaf.

Conclusion

	CD
Variety	0.083
*Stage	0.072
*Sampling time	0.072
*Inoculation	0.059

were collected 7, 10, and 15 days after inoculation (DI). Leaves from uninoculated seedlings served as control. Ethanol extracts were prepared by following the procedure described in Chandramohan et al 1967. Total phenol in the ethanol extract was estimated using Folin-ciocalteu reagent.

TNAU7124 contained more total phe, nol than ASD5, CO 40, and TN1 (Table 1). The percentage changes in total phenol in inoculated plants compared with uninoculated plants are presented in Table 2.

Total phenolic content of the four varieties increased. but not uniformly, with inoculation. It decreased with plant age. The interactions between variety and crop stage, variety and sampling time, variety and treatment were highly significant.

Ortho-dihydroxy level increased 7 DI in TNAU7124, ASD5, and CO 40. Tillering and boot leaf stage inoculation

Table 2. Percentage changes in total phenolics and ortho-dihydroxy phenol in rice varieties due to *X. oryzae* infection. ^a

Variety	Plant stage ^b	Changes (%) in content of					
		Phenol			Ortho-dihydroxy phenol		
		7 DI	10 DI	15 DI	7 DI	10 DI	15 DI
TNAU7124	S	+23.60	+13.15	+ 4.38	+12.12	+17.80	- 4.55
	T	+ 9.87	+10.78	+10.87	+68.75	+73.58	+16.27
	B	+15.54	+12.61	+16.26	+97.30	+ 1.39	+30.43
ASD5	S	+11.11	+23.45	+ 8.22	+15.71	-16.27	- 0.48
	T	+ 1.20	+ 3.59	- 1.38	+67.80	+30.26	+16.91
	B	+ 0.76	- 0.81	- 21.37	+22.46	+44.44	+16.48
TN1	S	+ 3.16	+17.06	+12.32	-20.00	+15.48	+14.69
	T	-15.45	-14.78	+ 8.53	+11.16	+12.70	+35.65
	B	+ 2.44	+ 7.84	- 5.56	- 2.60	+21.67	+60.66
CO 40	S	+ 7.96	- 6.71	-10.04	+25.87	+ 3.27	+ 3.27
	T	+ 8.23	+ 4.42	1.55	+19.40	+ 2.04	+56.70
	B	+ 1.31	+ 5.13	+ 6.67	+ 2.67	+ 0.98	-37.76

^a DI = days after inoculation. ^b S = seedling, T = tillering, B = boot leaf.

of TNAU7124 also caused accumulation of ortho-dihydroxy phenol. During last sampling ortho-dihydroxy phenol decreased except in TN1. Interactions be-

tween variety and stage, variety and sampling time, stage and sampling time, variety and treatment, and stage and treatment were significantly superior. □

Pest management and control INSECTS

Fungal pathogens of *Nephotettix virescens* Dist. and *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål

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The potential benefits of biological insect pest control methods, especially those using bacteria and viruses, are well known. Fungi are now explored as a control method for certain insects, including green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* and brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*.

GLH and BPH were found dead in unsprayed standing rice crops during cold months. Specimens from 26 locations in Tamil Nadu and Kerala States, India, were collected and examined.

Dead insects showed mummification, changes in morphological characters, and outgrowth of fungal tissues. Specimens were washed in three changes of sterile water and plated in sterile agar medium

to isolate microorganisms. Nine species of fungi were isolated from GLH and six from BPH. Five species of fungi were common to both insect species (see table).

Pathogenicity tests showed that *Fusarium* sp., isolated from GLH, and *Cephalosporium* sp., isolated from BPH, caused infection and death of both insects 4-7 days after treatment. *Fusarium* sp. caused 72.4 and 48.3% mortality of GLH nymphs and adults and 67.3 and 40.0% mortality of BPH nymphs and adults. *Cephalosporium* sp. caused GLH mortality rate of 70.7 and 37.5% and killed 75.9 and 52.7%

Fungi isolated from *N. virescens* and *N. lugens*.

Species	Common to both
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	*
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	*
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	*
<i>Phoma</i> sp.	*
<i>Rhizopus</i> sp.	*
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	
<i>Alternaria tenuis</i>	
<i>Curvularia</i> sp.	
<i>Fusarium oxysporium</i>	
<i>Cephalosporium lecanii</i>	

BPH nymphs and adults. Spraying fungal suspension containing conidia and mycelia caused higher death rates than spraying the culture filtrate or treating the insects with fungal mass.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.